

Table 3. Karna grain yield in wet rice farm trials in Karnataka, 1981-83.

Year	Yield (t/ha)	
	Karna	IR20
1981	5.6	4.8
1982	6.3	6.0
1983	6.5	6.0
Av	6.1	5.6

IET7209 (KMP39)] showed resistance to blast (Bl), brown spot, stem borer, and gall midge. It was highly resistant to Bl in trials at Ponnampet, Karnataka, the hotspot for Bl (Table 1).

In 1979-84 yield trials at Mandya, Karna yielded an average 4.8 t/ha

compared with 4.2 t for IR20 (Table 2). In 1981-83 field trials at 30 sites, Karna yielded an average 6.1 t/ha compared with 5.6 t for IR20 (Table 3). At Mudgere, where Bl is endemic, it yielded an average 4.9 t/ha compared with 4.3 t for IR20. ☞

Mutagen-caused molecular losses in rice and reversal by gibberellic acid (GA)

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Dehusked IR8 seeds were treated with a 1% aqueous solution of ethyl methane sulphonate (EMS), methyl methane

sulphonate (MMS), and ethylene glycol (EG) for 6 and 12 h to determine their effect on germination, cell wall permeability, α -amylase activity, and amino acid and RNA contents. Reversal of mutagen effects was studied by GA (100/ μ g/ml) treatment.

Among the different mutagens, MMS significantly inhibited germination, α -amylase activity, RNA and amino acid content in both treatments, and

substantially increased cell wall permeability. EG reduced germination and other molecular degradation less than MMS or EMS, but significantly reduced amino acid content.

Applying GA to seeds treated for 6 h reversed the mutagens' effects and improved germination percentage and other molecular contents (see table). Mutagen treatment for 12 h could not be reversed by GA treatment. ☞

Change of molecular contents during germination after different mutagen treatments.^a

Treatment	Germination (%)	Leakage of ions (mmho)	OD values		
			α -amylase activity	Amino acid	RNA
EMS 6 h	69**	0.026*	0.21	0.067**	0.41*
MMS 6 h	46**	0.035**	0.25	0.047**	0.37**
EG 6 h	96	0.013	0.17	0.086**	0.57
GA 6 h	100	0.014	0.04**	0.163	0.78
EMS 6 h + GA 6 h	88* (27.53)	0.014 (46.15)	0.18 (14.28)	0.143 (113.43)	0.69 (68.29)
MMS 6 h + GA 6 h	63** (36.95)	0.018 (48.57)	0.21 (16.00)	0.102 (117.02)	0.65 (75.67)
EG 6 h + GA 6 h	98 (2.08)	0.012 (7.69)	0.16 (5.88)	0.150 (74.41)	0.71 (24.56)
EMS 12 h	56**	0.034**	0.23	0.052**	0.40*
MMS 12 h	40**	0.043**	0.26	0.041**	0.32**
EG 12 h	95	0.022*	0.18	0.068**	0.55
GA 12 h	100	0.015	0.04**	0.162	0.82*
EMS 12 h + GA 6 h	59** (5.35)	0.026* (23.52)	0.22 (4.34)	0.057** (9.61)	0.44* (10.00)
MMS 12 h + GA 6 h	46** (15.00)	0.032** (25.58)	0.24 (7.69)	0.045** (9.75)	0.36** (12.50)
EG 12 h + GA 6 h	98 (3.15)	0.017 (22.72)	0.17 (5.55)	0.073** (7.35)	0.57 (3.63)
Control 0 h	99	0.010	0.15	0.168	0.62
6 h	99	0.011	0.15	0.168	0.62
12 h	99	0.012	0.15	0.167	0.63

^ap value: *0.05; **0.01. Figures in parentheses indicate percent reversal by GA treatment.

KMS5914-4-6 (Sona Mahsuri): a semitall, fine-grain, high yielding rice variety to replace Mahsuri in Karnataka

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Sona Mahsuri (KMS5914-4-6) is replacing popular variety Mahsuri in Karnataka. It was developed from

Sons/Mahsuri, received through the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. Further selections were made for tight panicles and lodging resistance.

Sona Mahsuri is semitall and matures in 140-145 d. Plant type and panicle characters are similar to those of Mahsuri. It has compact tillering, fairly tight spikelets, and stiff straw.

Sona Mahsuri spikelets are brown and awnless. Kernels are medium-slender and 5.56 mm by 2.1 mm.

Table 1. Leaf Bl teaction of Sona Mahsuri at Ponnampet, 1982-84.

Year	Bl rating	
	Sona Mahsuri	Intan
1982	4.0	9.0
1983	2.0	5.7
1984	1.6	3.0
Av	2.5	5.9

Length-to-breadth ratio is 2.56; that of Mahsuri is 2.45. Grains are translucent